

Training young basketball players according to their individual characteristics

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Abstract

The article addresses the issue of individualizing the training process in basketball. It demonstrates that training cannot be identical for ten-year-old and thirty-year-old players, as the physical, psychological, and technical characteristics of athletes differ significantly at various stages of their development. This seemingly obvious fact is not always taken into account in practice, especially by novice coaches.

The author emphasizes a common mistake - replicating training programs designed for adult teams when working with children and adolescents, which can reduce training effectiveness and even lead to injuries. The paper analyzes the main individual characteristics of players according to their playing positions, physical and psychological preparedness, and suggests approaches to structuring the training process while taking into account individual characteristics. The presented data and tables can serve as methodological guidelines for coaches working at different stages of athlete development.

Keywords: Training, competition, aspiration, rapid growth phases, players, mini-basketball, cognitive skills, intellectual maturity.

Introduction

Modern basketball requires not only physical fitness but also a high level of technical, tactical, and psychological development of players. In youth basketball, it is especially important to consider the individual characteristics of athletes, as it is at this age that the foundations of future mastery, attitude towards sports, and motivation for the training process are laid. A uniform approach to training can hinder the development of some players and overburden others, therefore individualizing training becomes a key factor in effectiveness. A coach should never forget the following principle: training must be adapted to the characteristics of the players participating in it. Therefore, the training of ten-year-old players can never be the same as that of thirty-year-olds. This objective fact, although simple, is not always clearly applied in practice.

The problem is that many novice coaches try to replicate the training of adult teams or create very similar training structures. This can occur due to a lack of ideas or a poor under-

standing of coaching approaches.

Objective of the work: To develop a sports training program and optimize training loads for basketball players at the initial stage of preparation.

Research methods: Analysis and synthesis of scientific and methodological literature; pedagogical experiment and methods of mathematical statistics.

Object of ResearchThe training process of young basketball players aged 8-10 years at the initial stage of sports preparation.

Subject of Research-Individualization of training loads and its impact on the level of physical fitness of basketball players aged 8-10 years.

The research results can be used by coaches of children's and youth sports schools when planning the training process at the initial stage of basketball players' preparation. Training should be structured taking into account the developmental stages by age: **6-9 years** - a period of general physical development and introduction to the game. The main emphasis is placed on coordination, agility, game-based forms of learning, and developing interest in basketball; **10-12 years** - active development of motor skills. Basic technical elements (dribbling, passing, shooting) are introduced, and proper technique is formed. **13-15 years** - a period of intensive growth and puberty. It requires a cautious approach to workloads, increased attention to technique, and injury prevention. **16-18 years** - the stage of sports specialization, development of tactical thinking and individual playing style.

"Training is a purposeful developmental process that should be conducted with consideration of the initial fitness level of athletes and age-related limitations. Beginner players aged 8-13 are in the first phase of ontogenetic development, which is most favorable for the formation of cognitive functions and the improvement of motor skills (approximately up to 11 years old). Subsequently, a period of age-related restructuring of the body occurs, caused

Table. Indicators Dynamics of physical fitness indicators of young basketball players aged 8-10 during the pedagogical experiment n=24

No.	Test	Group	Before the experiment $\bar{X} \pm \sigma$	After the experiment $\bar{X} \pm \sigma$	t	p
1.	30m Run, s	CG	6.1 ± 0.4	6.0 ± 0.4	1.12	>0.05
		EG	6.0 ± 0.3	5.6 ± 0.3	3.45	<0.01
2.	Shuttle run 3×10 m, s	CG	10.8 ± 0.6	10.6 ± 0.5	1.38	>0.05
		EG	10.7 ± 0.5	10.1 ± 0.4	3.92	<0.01
3.	Standing long jump, cm	CG	135 ± 11	140 ± 11	1.54	>0.05
		EG	138 ± 11	152 ± 10	4.18	<0.001
4.	Ball throw (1 kg), m	CG	5.6 ± 0.7	5.9 ± 0.6	1.26	>0.05
		EG	5.8 ± 0.6	6.7 ± 0.5	3.67	<0.01
5.	Seated forward bend, cm	CG	4.2 ± 1.1	4.8 ± 1.0	1.41	>0.05
		EG	4.5 ± 1.0	6.3 ± 0.9	4.05	<0.001
6.	6-minute run, m	CG	850 ± 60	880 ± 55	1.33	>0.05
		EG	860 ± 55	940 ± 50	3.88	<0.01

by a phase of intensive growth, which can be accompanied by a temporary decrease in motor and coordination abilities." In general, this type of player is characterized by: Good body awareness and control; however, considering the rapid growth phase, the ability to fully control their body and coordination develops over time. A strong competitive drive that contributes to their sports practice. In general, this type of player is characteristic: Good knowledge of their body, ability to control it, however, taking into account the passage of the rapid growth phase, the ability to control their body and coordination comes with time.

The physical characteristics of young players differ significantly in terms of height, strength level, speed, and endurance. These differences are especially noticeable during adolescence. Tall players are often more effective in playing under the basket, but need to develop coordination, footwork, and ball handling technique; Short and fast players are usually strong in dribbling and defense, and it's important for them to develop shooting skills and game awareness; Physically strong players can dominate in the early stages, but it's important for the coach not to limit their development solely to physical battles. Individual exercise selection and load management help avoid overexertion and promote well-rounded development.

The coach plays a key role in the process of individualizing training. They must possess knowledge in the fields of pedagogy, psychology, and sports physiology, and be able to analyze the characteristics of each athlete. The effective work of a coach involves: regular observation of players' developmental progress; adjustment of training loads; use of individualized tasks; and interaction with parents and medical

specialists.

The pedagogical experiment was conducted over a 3-week period. The study involved 24 young basketball players aged 8-10 years, divided into control and experimental groups. The control group trained according to the traditional program, while the experimental group followed a program with elements of individualized training loads, taking into account age and individual characteristics.

To test the effectiveness of an individualized approach to the training process, control and experimental groups were formed from young basketball players aged 8-10 years.

We will now examine the dynamics of indicators during and after the experiment for these young basketball players (Table 1).

The significance of differences between the indicators before and after the pedagogical experiment was determined using Student's t-test for dependent samples. The level of statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Analysis of the dynamics of physical fitness indicators showed that in the control group, the changes were positive but statistically insignificant ($p > 0.05$). In the experimental group, after the completion of the pedagogical experiment, statistically significant improvements were observed in all studied indicators ($p < 0.01-0.001$). The research results are consistent with the principles of developmental pedagogy and sports training theory, according to which the initial stage of preparation requires special attention to a child's individual capabilities. At ages 8-10, children are in an active phase of motor skill development, while differences in the rates of physical development can be quite significant.

The application of an individualized approach made it possible to optimize training

loads, enhance their pedagogical focus, and create conditions for a more harmonious development of physical qualities. The use of game-based and variable exercises helped maintain high motivation for training sessions and actively engage children in the training process.

Thus, individualization serves not only as a means of increasing the effectiveness of physical training but also as an important pedagogical factor in fostering a lasting interest in basketball.

Conclusion

Training young basketball players with consideration of their individual characteristics is a necessary condition for effective and safe development. This approach allows unlocking the potential of each player, increasing motivation, reducing the risk of injuries, and creating a solid foundation for further sporting growth.

Individualization of the training process is an effective pedagogical tool for improving the level of physical fitness of 8-10-year-old basketball players at the initial stage of preparation. Individualization of training is an investment not only in results but also in the child's personal development. The application of age-appropriate and individualized workloads ensures a statistically significant increase in indicators of speed, coordination, speed-strength qualities, and endurance, contributes to comprehensive development, improvement of sports results, and the formation of a stable interest in basketball. It enhances the quality of the training process and ensures the harmonious development of the young athlete's personality.

The developed approach to organizing training sessions can be recommended for practical use in children's and youth sports schools and is a crucial condition for the effective preparation of athletes.

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Research interests

Basketball, physical education and sport, Theory of physical education, Analyzing of sport competitions.